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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY ON DYKE-DAVID DISORDER OFF-
MASSON**¹Dr Fahim Ahmad Danish, ¹Dr Shafiq Ahmed Khan, ²Dr Hadila Zafar¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore²AIMTH Sialkot**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Dyke-Davidoff-Mason disorder was analyzed in a multi-year old child who gave a history of summarized seizures since the age of 5 months. The critical birth history included delayed crying and a 30-day stay in the emergency unit. Results were delayed. After assessment, vital signs were stable. Head circumference was estimated to be 44 cm (< - 3 SD for age). There were no neurocutaneous markers. The child had left a hemiparesis with energetic ligament reflexes and an extensor plantar reflex. Our research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from October 2018 to September 2019. The CT scan revealed hemi atrophy on the right side with ipsilateral falx movement. Sulcus spaces and ventricular framework on a similar side were unequivocal. The overlying calvarium was thickened.

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INTRODUCTION:

Dyke-Davidoff-Masson syndrome is an uncommon epileptic disorder characterized by overwhelming signs of seizures, facial asymmetry, hemi atrophy, contralateral hemiparesis, thickening of the cranial vault and mental handicap [1]. Masson tumor (intravascular papillary endothelial hyperplasia) is a rare proliferation of endothelial cells within the wall of a vessel, often thought to represent an aberrant resolution of a thrombosis [2]. Wyburn-Mason syndrome is an extremely rare nonhereditary disorder that is present at birth (congenital). Affected infants have arteriovenous malformations (AVMs), which are developmental abnormalities affecting the blood vessels, specifically the arteries, veins and capillaries. Arteries typically carry oxygen-rich blood from the heart to body cells, while veins transport oxygen-deficient blood to the heart and lungs for the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide. The network of very tiny blood vessels (capillaries) that normally connects arteries and veins may be absent and the arteries and veins may be directly linked together [3-4]. Larger AVMs may consist of a tangled mass of abnormal or malformed blood vessels. AVMs associated with Wyburn-Mason syndrome are usually found in the eyes and midbrain. The exact cause of Wyburn-Mason syndrome is unknown [5].

CASE REPORT:

A male child of two years of age, 1st birth application and conceived of a non-consanguineous marriage, submitted to our administrations with a summary seizure history since the age of 5 months. The birth history was huge, with delayed crying and a 30-day stay in the emergency services. Achievements were postponed. After assessment, vital signs were stable. Head circumference was estimated at 44 cm (< 3 SD for age). There were no neurocutaneous markers. The youngster had left hemiparesis with energetic ligament reflexes and an extensor plantar reflex. The child had left a hemiparesis with energetic ligament reflexes and an extensor plantar reflex. Our research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from October 2018 to September 2019. Cranial nerves and CSF assessment were normal. The CT scan showed hemi atrophy on the right side with ipsilateral falx displacement (bolt in Figure 1). Sulcus spaces and ventricular framework on a similar side were unequivocal. The overlying calvarium was thickened (bolt in Fig. 2). Based on these findings, Dyke-Davidoff-Mason's disorder was determined and the youngster began anticonvulsant therapy.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

DISCUSSION:

Dyke-Davidoff-Mason's disease, first described in 1935, is characterized by unilateral cerebral decay with compensatory hypertrophy of the overlying skull and hyper pneumatization of the ipsilateral sinuses. The atrophic cortex presents an undeniable quality of ventricular framework and sulcus spaces. There is a slight male dominance. The patient presents with seizures, contralateral hemiparesis and mental discomfort. Seizures may be central or

summarized. Manifestations include facial asymmetry, learning disability, mental objections and embarrassed speech. Deterioration of the cerebral stitching may be the result of an obstruction of the central cerebral supply pathway due to contamination or formative strangeness (the intrinsic shape) [6]. The supplied assortment is the result of injuries, tumour, contamination, ischemia, rejection in addition, prolonged febrile seizure. It is the start time of the events that separates the two.

In addition, the inherent assortment of the disease is close to a unilateral calvarial thickening. It is accepted that this enlargement of the diploid space is supposed to compensate for bone development due to the void created by the atrophic neuroparenchyma [7-8]. Differences include: a) Sturge-Weber's Disorder (cerebral decay associated with leptogenic angioma and proximity to a port wine facial nevus, intracranial calcification of the tracheal pathways, and non-appearance of medial motion) and b) Rasmussen's Encephalitis (unilateral hemispherical decay without calvaria change with immobile epilepsy). The various fewer basic differentials are the right nevus, Fishman's disorder and basal ganglion germinoma [9]. An appropriate history, careful clinical evaluation and imaging findings guarantee the result. The treatment of a child with Dyke-Davidoff-Mason's disease includes epilepsy medication, physiotherapy and speech restoration [10]. Hemispherectomy is performed when cases are immobile. It is safe to assume that there are no recurrent seizures and that the onset of hemiparesis follows age 2 years.

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